

Mixed Chelate and Ternary Complexes of Nickel(II)

(Miss) MINATI BARAL, B. K. KANUNGO and B. PRADHAN*

Department of Chemistry, Regional Engineering College, Rourkela-769 008

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A series of complexes of the type $Ni(AA')(BB')L$ and $Ni(AA')(BB')L_2$, where AA' =diethyldithio-carbamate (et_2dtc); BB' =acetylacetonate ($acac$), 8-hydroxy-quinolate (ox), dimethylglyoximate (dmg), pyridinecarboxylate ($pyca$); and L =water or pyridine-*N*-oxide ($pyNO$), have been isolated by the reaction of nickel(II) salts with suitable ligands in stoichiometric ratio. The compounds were characterised on the basis of their analyses, molecular weight, molar conductance, magnetic susceptibility, infrared and electronic spectral data. Compounds having composition $Ni(AA')(BB')$ were found to be tetraordinated, $Ni(AA')(BB')L$ pentacoordinated and $Ni(AA')(BB')L_2$ hexacoordinated.

NICKEL(II) ion usually prefers four- and six-coordination under normal condition¹. However, under suitable ligand fields, it is known to stabilise the pentacoordinate complexes². The versatility of the chelates such as diethyldithiocarbamate, acetylacetonate, oxinate, pyridine carboxylate and dimethylglyoximate, and ligands such as pyridine-*N*-oxide is well known³⁻⁶. In the present communication, it was intended to investigate the behaviour of nickel(II) ion in presence of two uninegative chelating agents with hetero-donor atoms and further study its preference in presence of an additional third neutral monodentate ligand thus providing it with a ternary ligand system.

Experimental

Preparation of complexes :

$Ni(et_2dtc)(acac)H_2O$, $Ni(et_2dtc)(ox)H_2O$, $Ni(et_2dtc)(dmg)$, $Ni(et_2dtc)(pyca)$: To an ethanolic solution of $NiCl_2 \cdot 6H_2O$, equimolecular mixture of sodium salt of diethyldithiocarbamate and acetyl acetone/oxine/dimethylglyoxime/pyridine carboxylic acid in ethanol was added with stirring. A dilute solution of ammonia was added dropwise till the complexes separated out which were suction-filtered through sintered glass crucible, washed with ethanol, ether and dried in vacuum.

$Ni(et_2dtc)(acac)(pyNO)$, $Ni(et_2dtc)(ox)(pyNO)$, $Ni(et_2dtc)(dmg)(pyNO)$, $Ni(et_2dtc)(pyca)(pyNO)_2$, $Ni(ox)(pyca)(pyNO)_2$: Ethanolic suspension of $Ni(et_2dtc)(acac)H_2O$, $Ni(et_2dtc)(ox)H_2O$, $Ni(et_2dtc)(dmg)$, $Ni(et_2dtc)(pyca)$, $Ni(ox)(pyca)$ and ethanolic solution of pyridine-*N*-oxide in 1:2 molar ratio were refluxed for 2 h, and then cooled and suction-filtered through sintered glass crucible, washed with ethanol, ether and dried in vacuum.

Infrared spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer as KBr optics. Electronic spectra in $\sim 10^{-3} M$ acetone solution was recorded by an automatic Perkin-Elmer 202 instrument within

200–450 nm and by a Elico spectrophotometer in the region 450–900 nm. Magnetic susceptibility measurements were carried out at 300 K by a Gouy balance using $Hg[Co(NCS)_4]$ as the calibrant. The diamagnetic corrections were calculated by using Pascal's constants⁷. The conductance measurements were carried out in $\sim 10^{-3} M$ acetone solution using a Systronics 303 direct reading conductivity meter. The molecular weight measurements were carried out by Rast's method using biphenyl as solvent. The results of elemental analyses and physico-chemical measurements are given in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

The complexes prepared were either flaky or microcrystalline. All the compounds except $Ni(et_2dtc)(dmg)$ melted around 250°. These were soluble in acetone and sparingly soluble in most organic solvents. The zero value of molar conductance (Λ_m) in acetone medium of the complexes indicates that they are essentially non-electrolytes. The molecular weight measurement indicated that the penta- and hexa-coordinate compounds were monomeric in nature. On the basis of their behaviour towards magnetic field, these Ni^{II} complexes could be divided into four categories: (i) four-coordinated diamagnetic with μ_{eff} value slightly higher than zero, (ii) five-coordinated paramagnetic with μ_{eff} lying below the spin-only momentum, (iii) five-coordinated paramagnetic complexes with μ_{eff} above the spin-only momentum, and (iv) six-coordinated paramagnetic with μ_{eff} value higher than the spin-only momentum (2.82 B.M.) as expected for two unpaired electrons. For the four-coordinate complexes, two stereochemistries, tetrahedral one with two unpaired electrons and diamagnetic square-planar complexes with $\mu_{eff}=0$, are known. The μ_{eff} value for $Ni(et_2dtc)(dmg)$ and $Ni(et_2dtc)(pyca)$ were found to be 0.63 and 0.91 B.M., respectively. In these compounds the small paramagnetism may be attributed to the thermal population of a triplet

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL, MOLAR CONDUCTANCE, MAGNETIC DATA AND ELECTRONIC SPECTRA OF NICKEL(II) COMPLEXES

Sl. no.	Complex	Colour	Molecular weight Found/ (Calcd.)	M.p. °C	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		μ_{eff}° at 300 K B.M.	λ_{max} (cm ⁻¹)
					Ni	S		
1.	Ni(et ₂ dte)(acac).H ₂ O	Green	305.00 (324.11)	240	17.5 (18.1)	18.9 (19.7)	2.61	11 458, 12 195, 13 983, 26 315
2.	Ni(et ₂ dte)(ox).H ₂ O	Green	345.00 (369.15)	250	16.2 (15.9)	17.1 (17.3)	2.56	11 528, 12 195, 13 785, 26 315
3.	Ni(et ₂ dte)(dmg)	Scarlet red	402.00 (322.99)	> 300	18.5 (18.1)	20.0 (19.8)	0.68	15 873, 23 255, 27 027
4.	Ni(et ₂ dte)(pyca)	Green	395.00 (329.09)	235	17.7 (17.8)	19.3 (19.4)	0.91	16 528, 22 988, 26 666
5.	Ni(et ₂ dte)(acac)(pyNO)	Green	405.00 (401.09)	230	15.0 (14.6)	15.6 (15.9)	2.37	11 627, 12 195, 14 285, 26 315
6.	Ni(et ₂ dte)(ox)(pyNO)	Green	430.00 (446.15)	235	12.7 (13.1)	14.5 (14.3)	2.57	11 363, 12 195, 13 513, 26 315
7.	Ni(et ₂ dte)(dmg)(pyNO)	Scarlet red	395.00 (417.98)	270	13.5 (14.0)	15.1 (15.3)	3.34	11 627, 12 195, 13 513, 26 315
8.	Ni(et ₂ dte)(pyca)(pyNO) ₂	Green	525.00 (519.19)	225	11.5 (11.3)	12.0 (12.3)	3.05	12 500 (ν_1), 15 625 (ν_2), 26 315 (ν_3)
9.	Ni(ox)(pyca)(pyNO) ₂	Green	502.00 (515.08)	> 300	11.8 (11.4)	12.0 (12.4)	3.13	12 195 (ν_1), 14 705 (ν_2), 26 315 (ν_3)

which lies very close to the singlet ground state⁹. It may also be due to their tendency towards polymerisation in solid state leading to weak coordination in axial direction resulting in tetrahedral distortion which is indicated by the relatively higher values of molecular weights of these compounds than the expected value for monomeric species. Among the pentacoordinate complexes reported in this investigation, Ni(et₂dte)(dmg)(pyNO) showed the normal magnetic moment (Table 1) as expected for five-coordinate Ni^{II} complexes (3.2–3.4 B.M.). The other pentacoordinate complexes, viz. Sl. nos. 1, 2, 5, 6 (Table 1), showed magnetic moment between 2.37–2.6 B.M., which is lower than the expected value for two unpaired electrons but higher than that of zero unpaired electron. In pentacoordinate environment, fields in axial direction is weak and hence the separation between $d_{x^2-y^2}$ and d_{z^2} orbital is more resulting in singlet state and lowering of paramagnetism. The abnormal magnetic behaviour of metal complexes in the presence of dithiocarbamate is well known which causes spin-free $\rightleftharpoons$ spin-paired equilibrium⁹⁻¹². The six-coordinate octahedral paramagnetic complexes (with two unpaired electrons) with ground term ${}^3A_{2g}$ should show magnetic moments which are given by the term $2.83(1-4N/10Dq)$, i.e. some 10% above the spin-only value for $S=1$ (2.82 B.M.), since $\lambda = -315 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. Extensive work¹³⁻¹⁵ shows that moments for octahedral complexes are found mostly between 2.9 and 3.3 B.M. In this investigation for the hexacoordinated complexes Ni(dte)(pyca)(pyNO)₂ and Ni(ox)(pyca)(pyNO)₂, the moment value was found to be 3.05 and 3.13 B.M., respectively, as expected for spin-free nickel(II).

Infrared spectra: Many bands due to oxine, picolonic acid and dimethylglyoxime are found to be superimposed on the bands of dithiocarbamate.

However, most characteristic bands which could be distinctly assigned to different ligands are discussed below. Dithiocarbamate is known to behave as a bidentate as well as a monodentate ligand. The former exhibits $\nu_{\text{C-S}}$ near 1000 cm^{-1} as a single band, whereas the latter shows a doublet in the same region¹⁶. Also, the $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ of the former (above 1485 cm^{-1}) is higher than that of the latter (below 1485 cm^{-1})¹⁷. In the present case, the $\nu_{\text{C-S}}$ band was obtained at ~ 990 and $\sim 1000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ as a single band and $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ band was found above 1485 cm^{-1} in all the complexes, indicating that diethyldithiocarbamate is coordinated to nickel(II) as an uninegative bidentate ligand. The M—S stretching frequency in transition metal dithiocarbamate is located at about 350 cm^{-1} ^{18,19}. The band observed at $\sim 280 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in all the complexes may be due to Ni—S stretching vibration which also confirms the coordination of dithiocarbamate. In the acetylacetonate chelates of nickel(II), the $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ band was found at $\sim 1610 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $\nu_{\text{C=C}}$ at 1560 cm^{-1} indicating that the ligand was coordinated to the metal ion as uninegative bidentate fashion as suggested by Graddon⁴. In the present investigation, the invariable presence of a strong band in the oxinate compounds at 1105 cm^{-1} definitely indicates the coordination of the ligand through nitrogen and oxygen atoms behaving as uninegative bidentate one²⁰. In the complexes containing pyridinecarboxylic acid, the band due to free COOH group was found to be absent. Other bands due to $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{COO}^-)$ and pyridine ring was found to be present at 1610 cm^{-1} as observed by Fowles *et al.*²¹. This suggests that picolonic acid is coordinated to the metal ion through oxygen and nitrogen atoms as uninegative bidentate chelating agent. In the complexes containing dimethylglyoxime, ν_{OH} was found at 1690 cm^{-1} indicating that it also

behaves as an uninegative bidentate one²¹. Bands due to pyridine-*N*-oxide were obtained at $\sim 1\,200$, $790-840$ and $740-780\text{ cm}^{-1}$ which can be assigned as $\nu_{\text{N-O}}$, $\delta_{\text{N-O}}$ and $\nu_{\text{C-H}}$ ²²⁻²⁵. Bands due to coordinated water²⁶ was observed at ~ 830 and $\sim 3\,400\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the complexes $\text{Ni}(\text{et}_2\text{dtc})(\text{acac})\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{Ni}(\text{et}_2\text{dtc})(\text{ox})\text{H}_2\text{O}$. In all other tetra- and penta-coordinated complexes the above two bands were found to be absent indicating that water was not coordinated to the metal ion and supports the confirmity of the coordination number.

Electronic spectra: The electronic spectra are of more diagnostic value for the coordination number of the compounds. Octahedral and six-coordinate nickel(II) complexes exhibit three spin-allowed transitions²⁷ at $7\,000-13\,000$ (ν_1), $11\,000-20\,000$ (ν_2) and $19\,000-27\,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (ν_3) arising from ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)$, ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3A_{1g}(F)$ and ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ transitions, respectively. The bands obtained due to the two six-coordinate compounds, viz. Sl. nos. 8 and 9 (Table 1), are fairly in agreement with the above observations. The two four-coordinate compounds, viz. Sl. nos. 3 and 4 (Table 1) were found to exhibit bands at $\sim 16\,000$ (ν_1), $\sim 23\,000$ (ν_2) and $\sim 27\,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (ν_3) which are in agreement with the square-planar configurations and may be assigned to ${}^1A_{1g}(D) \rightarrow {}^1A_{2g}(G)$, ${}^1A_{1g}(D) \rightarrow {}^1B_{2g}(D)$, ${}^1A_{1g}(D) \rightarrow {}^1E_g(G)$ transitions respectively, as suggested by Lever²⁷ and Maki²⁸. Compounds Sl. nos. 1, 2, 5, 6 and 7 (Table 1) showed bands at $8\,000$, $10\,000$, $13\,000$ and $16\,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ as observed for penta-coordinated Ni^{II} complexes^{29,30}. The ternary complexes usually preferred six-coordination when one of the chelating agents was pyridine-carboxylic acid, whereas others were found to be pentacoordinated.

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